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Report: NET-Fuels 1st Stakeholders Workshop

Terrassa / Barcelona, Spain - November 9th, 2023

Dissemination Level: Public

NET- Fuels | INCREASING BIOMASS CONVERSION EFFICIENCY TO CARBON-NEGATIVE SUSTAINABLE BIOFUELS BY COMBINATION OF THERMOCHEMICAL AND BIO-ELECTROCHEMICAL PROCESSES

HORIZON-CL5-2021-D3-03-09 | GRANT AGREEMENT NUMBER: 101083780

Report:

NET-Fuels 1st Stakeholders Workshop

Dissemination Level		
PU	Public	x

Document Type		
R	Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)	x

Submission date: 27/11/2023
Reference Period: 09/11/2023
Report Lead Partner: REACH Innovation
Contributions: Leitat, WRG

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General Information

GA Number: 101083780
Start date of project: 01/11/2022
Project Duration: 4 years
Project website: www.net-fuels.eu or www.netfuels.project.org

NET-Fuels consortium

Short	Beneficiary	Role
UNIBO	Alma Mater Studiorum – Università di Bologna	CO
FRA	Fraunhofer UMSICHT	BEN
LEITAT	Acondicionamiento Tarrasense (Leitat)	BEN
SUT	Silesian University of Technology	BEN
ITHAKA	Ithaka Institute	BEN
REACH	REACH Innovation	BEN
WRG	WRG Europe	AP

CO...Coordinator, BEN...Beneficiary, AP...Associated Partner

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Executive Summary

This document reports about the 1st NET-Fuels Stakeholders Community Workshop, organized by the NET-Fuels Consortium at Leitat Technological Center in Terrassa / Barcelona, Spain, on November 9th, 2023.

The 1st NET-Fuels Stakeholders Community Workshop is part of the planned activities of the Exploitation Plan devised for the NET-Fuels project, under the lead of REACH Innovation (NET-Fuels exploitation partner).

As part of NET-Fuels project's "Open Science" concept as a Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Action, this Report, as a public dissemination-level document, will be made available in the NET-Fuels' open-access research data repository within the Zenodo NET-Fuels Community (https://zenodo.org/communities/net_fuels_horizon_europe_project/), for further reference and dissemination.

1 Introduction

1.1 NET-Fuels Project Overview

NET-Fuels: “Increasing Biomass Conversion Efficiency to Carbon-Negative Sustainable Biofuels by Combination of Thermochemical and Bio-Electrochemical Processes”.

Creating carbon-negative fuels by novel thermal and chemical conversion of waste biomass

PROJECT SUMMARY

NET-Fuels is a 4-year project funded by the European Commission's Horizon Europe programme to develop and validate integrated thermochemical and bioelectrochemical processes to produce sustainable fuels from low-grade waste biomass. The system is designed to use process CO₂ for e-fuel generation and for certified CO₂ removal through the application of the process biochar to soil as a carbon sink.

Integration of ThermoCatalytic Reforming (TCR), oxyfuel combustion, and Bioelectrochemical Methanation (BEM).

BIO-REFINERY

Reducing process CO₂ by using biochar for soil amendment and certified carbon removal.

CARBON CAPTURE

To comprehensively validate the technologies to ensure a future pathway to pilot-scale demonstration and, ultimately, commercial exploitation.

VALIDATION

Coordinator

Project Team

Funded by the European Union

www.netfuelsproject.org

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The NET-Fuels project is funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe Energy programme (HORIZON-CL5-2021-D3-03-09, G.A. Nr.101083780 - URL: www.net-fuels.eu) and aims at increasing biomass conversion efficiency to carbon-negative sustainable biofuels by combination of thermal and bio-electrochemical processes. The project started on November 1st, 2022 and will end on October 30th, 2026. NET-Fuels is co-producing fuels and basic chemicals such as methane, hydrogen and oxygen as well as biochar, and with that negative emissions by combining pyrolysis of residual biomass and a power-to-gas approach.

NET-Fuels is a **power-to-gas** project providing solutions in the field of **carbon capture and utilisation and storage**. The technology also generates synthetic **methane, oxygen, and hydrogen**. The process will generate as an additional intermediate, a high-quality pyrolysis oil that has a proven conversion pathway to drop-in fuels. The project will take the integrated process to Technology Readiness Level 5, providing a platform (in terms of technical feasibility, economic performance, and environmental and social sustainability) for future pre-commercial demonstration and validation projects.

The long-term goal of the Net-Fuels technology is to provide 25 Mt of advanced biofuels by 2030 (a 7% share of transport fuel consumption), exploiting between one third and one quarter of the total pool of available residual biomass. At this target, NET-Fuels will guarantee 110 Mt CO₂ negative net emissions.

The NET-Fuels project is coordinated by the University of Bologna and is being executed by an international consortium of experts in thermochemical conversion of biomass, bioreactor design, environmental sustainability and life cycle analysis, dynamic modelling, biochar utilisation, economic analysis and business case development, as well as dissemination, awareness, public engagement and social sustainability analysis.

1.2 NET-Fuels Stakeholders Community

The management of the NET-Fuels Stakeholders Community is part of the exploitation activities of the project, led by partner REACH. The project selects organizations to be members of the NET-Fuels Exploitation Stakeholder Community (without any binding commitment on their part), with focus on the existing synergies of the operating sector and the expertise of the institutions in the field of the project.

The group of selected stakeholders embed organizations interested in biomass exploitation, as well as in the production of sustainable fuels and energy from low-grade residual biomass. It includes energy companies, research organisations, as well as refineries.

As a member of the NET-Fuels' Exploitation Stakeholder Community, the selected institution will be informed preferentially about the project's open-access developments, via its newsletters and public information releases. It is the responsibility of the exploitation partner of the NET-Fuels project (REACH) to establish an open channel with the members of the NET-Fuels' Exploitation Stakeholder Community and to update the project partners about potential constructive interactions that may occur therein throughout the project lifetime. Also, whenever project workshops or events open to stakeholders are organized, the Exploitation Stakeholder Community will be informed with sufficient notice for potential participation. The project, however, does not commit to any expenses for members participation in those activities.

2 NET-Fuels 1st Stakeholders Community Workshop

WORKSHOP: "NET-Fuels 1st Stakeholders Community Workshop"
 DATE / TIME: November 9, 2023 - 9:30 to 12:45 CEST
 VENUE: Leitat Technological Center. Carrer de la Innovació, 2, 08225 Terrassa, Barcelona, Spain.

As part of the planned activities of the NET-Fuels Project Exploitation Plan, the first NET-Fuels Stakeholders Community Workshop, that happened in the end of the 1st year of the project, was co-organized by Leitat (event host), REACH (exploitation partner) and WRG (dissemination partner), with a twofold main goal:

- (1) At one hand to start interacting with the professionals in the related research and industrial communities that are interested in our project.
- (2) On the other hand, to inform the invited stakeholders about the project's on-going developments and envisaged outcomes, giving them also the possibility to present related work from their sides.

This way, the main aim focused at enriching our synergies and paving the way for our future exploitation phase.

This edition of the NET-Fuels Stakeholders Workshop was mainly devoted to the Spanish community of stakeholders, as the event took place at the Leitat Technological Center in Barcelona. Altogether, the workshop counted with the participation of 35 stakeholders, including the project partners.

2.1 The Workshop Agenda

The Workshop Agenda included an initial part with short presentations about the NET-Fuels project, followed by the presentations concerning the invited stakeholders' topics. After the presentations, a short Discussion Session followed with the closing of the workshop, entailed by a Networking Get-together Buffet. (See Figure with the NET-Fuels Stakeholders Workshop Final Agenda on the figure that follows.)

NET-Fuels

Increasing Biomass Conversion Efficiency to Carbon-Negative Sustainable Biofuels by Combination of Thermochemical and Bio-Electrochemical Processes

<https://www.netfuelsproject.org/>

WORKSHOP: "NET-Fuels 1st Stakeholders Community Workshop"

DATE / TIME: November 9, 2023 - 9:30 to 12:45 CEST

VENUE : LEITAT, Carrer de la Innovació, 2, 08225, Terrassa, Barcelona

ORGANIZERS: [LEITAT](#) (Host; NET-Fuels Development Partner); [REACH](#) (NET-Fuels Exploitation Partner); [WRG](#) (NET-Fuels Dissemination Partner)

COLLABORATION: All NET-Fuels Partners (<https://www.netfuelsproject.org/about.html>)

WORKSHOP AGENDA:

9:30 - 9:40: Opening act by event host (Eduard Borràs, [LEITAT](#)) and co-organizers

(Fatima Dargam, [REACH](#) & Mark Langley, [WRG](#))

9:40 - 10:10: Summary Presentation of the NET-Fuels Project Concept / Partners Roles / Estimated Results (Andrea Contin, [UNIBO](#))

10:10 - 10:50: Presentation of the NET-Fuels Technologies (Martin Meiller, [FRA](#) & Daniele Molognoni, [LEITAT](#))

10:50 - 11:00: Comments and Questions & Answers about NET-Fuels

11:00 - 11:15: Coffee Break

11:15 - 12:30: Presentations from invited Stakeholders (slots of 15 minutes)

11:15 - 11:30: Antonio Sánchez / [Cluster Bioenergia Catalunya](#): "Biofuels and derivatives projects in the current Oil & Gas industry"

11:30 - 11:45: Alejandra Cordova / [CETAQUA](#): "[SEMPRE-BIO](#), new cost-effective solutions to produce Biomethane"

11:45 - 12:00: Odei Goñi / [ENGIE Spain](#): "The [REGENERA project](#): development of hybrid energy storage technologies and predictive models to transform industries into decentralized points for renewable energy management"

12:00 - 12:15: Luis Rafael Lopez / [University of Girona](#): "Indoor CO₂ as renewable carbon source: Coupling indoor CO₂ direct air capture to microbial electrosynthesis technologies"

12:15 - 12:30: Erhard Perz / [SIMTECH](#): "Simulation of virtual use-cases for the research project [RESTORE](#) using the web-based process simulation platform [IPSE GO](#)"

12:30 - 12:45: Q&A - Open Discussions - Workshop Closing Session by project coordinator ([UNIBO](#)), event host ([LEITAT](#)) and co-organizers ([REACH](#) & [WRG](#))

12:45: Buffet & Networking

NET-Fuels Project Consortium warmly thanks the external guests for their participation and potential feedback!

Coordinator

Project Team

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3 Workshop Presentations

3.1 Workshop Recording

The event was recorded and the final edited video of the "NET-Fuels 1st Stakeholders Community Workshop" presentations can be found in YouTube.

NET-Fuels 1st Stakeholders Community Workshop (complete video)

Link: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=QgV_WPr_CT4

Recording Sequence:

- 1) Opening act by event host (Eduard Borràs, Leitat) - [Recording 0:00 - 3:30]
- 2) Summary Presentation of the NET Fuels Project Concept / Partners Roles / Estimated Results (Andrea Contin, UNIBO) - [Recording 3:30 - 27:00]
- Presentation of the NET Fuels Technologies:
- 3) Martin Meiller, FRAUNHOFER - [Recording 27:00 - 52:00]
- 4) Daniele Molognoni, Leitat - [Recording 52:00 - 1:07:00]
- 5) Comments and Questions & Answers about NET Fuels - [Recording 1:07:00 - 1:18:00]
- 6) Presentations from invited Stakeholders (INTRO): [Recording 1:18:00 - 1:19:00]
- 7) Antonio Sánchez / Cluster Bioenergia Catalunya: Biofuels and derivatives projects in the current Oil & Gas industry - [Recording 1:19:00 - 1:31:00]
- 8) Alejandra Cordova / CETAQUA: SEMPRE BIO, new cost-effective solutions to produce Biomethane - [Recording 1:32:00 - 1:45:00]
- 9) Odei Goñi / ENGIE Spain: "The REGENERA project development of hybrid energy storage technologies and predictive models to transform industries into decentralized points for renewable energy management" - [Recording 1:45:00 - 2:03:00]
- 10) Luis Rafael Lopez / University of Girona: "Indoor CO2 as renewable carbon source: Coupling indoor CO2 direct air capture to microbial electrosynthesis technologies" - [Recording 2:03:00 - 2:20:00]
- 11) Erhard Perz / SIMTECH: "Simulation of virtual use cases for the research project RESTORE using the web-based process simulation platform IPSE GO" - [Recording 2:21:00 - 2:43:00]
- 12) Q&A Open Discussions Workshop Closing Session by project coordinator (UNIBO), event host (Leitat) and co-organizers (REACH & WRG) - [Recording 2:43:00 - 2:55:00]

3.2 Presentations

3.2.1 Presentation from UNIBO (NET-Fuels Coordinator)

Presentation of the “NET-Fuels Project Concept / Partners Roles / Estimated Results” by Andrea Contin (UNIBO): **See Annex 1.**

Andrea Contin (UNIBO – NET-Fuels Coordinator)

Andrea Contin (UNIBO)

3.2.2 Presentations from FRA UMSICHT and from Leitat (NET-Fuels Technologies)

Presentation by Martin Meiller (FRA UMSICHT): “By developing new technologies, we contribute to solving major challenges such as climate change, energy supply and raw material security”. See Annex 2.

Martin Meiller (Fraunhofer UMSICHT)

Presentation by Daniele Molognoni (Leitat): “Presentation of the NET Fuels Technologies: Bioelectrochemical Methanation”. See Annex 3.

Daniele Molognoni (Leitat)

3.2.3 Presentation from Cluster Bioenergia Catalunya

Presentation from the invited Stakeholder Antonio Sánchez from Cluster Bioenergia Catalunya: "Biofuels and derivatives projects in the current Oil & Gas industry". See Annex 4.

Antonio Sánchez (Cluster Bioenergia Catalunya)

3.2.4 Presentation from CETAQUA

Presentation from the invited Stakeholder Alejandra Cordova from CETAQUA: "SEMPRE-BIO, new cost-effective solutions to produce Biomethane". See Annex 5.

Alejandra Cordova (CETAQUA)

3.2.5 Presentation from ENGIE Spain

Presentation from the invited Stakeholder Odei Goñi from ENGIE Spain: "The REGENERA project: development of hybrid energy storage technologies and predictive models to transform industries into decentralized points for renewable energy management". See Annex 6.

Odei Goñi (ENGIE Spain)

3.2.6 Presentation from the University of Girona

Presentation from the invited Stakeholder Luis Rafael Lopez from the University of Girona: "Indoor CO2 as renewable carbon source: Coupling indoor CO2 direct air capture to microbial electrosynthesis technologies". See Annex 7.

Luis Rafael Lopez (University of Girona)

3.2.7 Presentation from SIMTECH

Presentation from the invited Stakeholder Erhard Perz from SIMTECH: "Simulation of virtual use-cases for the research project RESTORE using the web-based process simulation platform IPSE GO". See Annex 8.

Erhard Perz (SIMTECH)

4 Some Photos of the Workshop *

Eduard Borràs (Leitat)

NET-Fuels Consortium Members representing REACH; FRA; Leitatz; UNIBO; ITHAKA; and SUT.

***Credits:** Photos were taken by members of REACH Innovation and of Leitat during the workshop.

****Data Protection Disclaimer:** All involved Partners and Stakeholders appearing on the pictures have no objection concerning the publication of the photos in this report.

*****Dissemination Material:** The workshop invitation, the Roll-up and Flyer were designed by WRG Europe.

5 Final Remarks

Overall, the NET-Fuels Consortium is very pleased with the successful flow of the 1st NET-Fuels Stakeholders Community Workshop, organized at Leitat Technological Center in Terrassa / Barcelona, on the occasion of the completion of the project's first year of development.

We acknowledge the preparation work of the Workshop Organization Team, and we need to thank in special Leitat and its involved members, for the great efforts made in hosting the event, and in contacting valuable representatives of the Spanish Stakeholders Community to participate on our workshop.

Last, but not least, we wish to express our sincere gratitude to the invited speakers and to the team of invited Stakeholders, who took active part in the event, especially the ones that enriched the workshop with interesting and insightful presentations of their organizations' research and innovation projects. MANY THANKS to you ALL!

From our side, as Exploitation Partner of the NET-Fuels project, REACH will maintain an open channel with the members of the *NET-Fuels' Stakeholders Community* and will update the project partners about potential constructive interactions that may evolve therein throughout the project lifetime.

REACH Innovation / NET-Fuels Exploitation Partner
/on behalf of the NET-Fuels Project Consortium

Annexes¹

- Annex 1 – Presentation Slides from UNIBO (NET-Fuels Coordinator)
- Annex 2 – Presentation Slides from Fraunhofer UMSICHT (NET-Fuels Partner)
- Annex 3 – Presentation Slides from Leitat (NET-Fuels Partner)
- Annex 4 – Presentation Slides from Cluster Bioenergia Catalunya
- Annex 5 – Presentation Slides from CETAQUA
- Annex 6 – Presentation Slides from ENGIE Spain
- Annex 7 – Presentation Slides from the University of Girona
- Annex 8 – Presentation Slides from SIMTECH

¹ The Workshop Presentation Slides from NET-Fuels Partners and from the invited Stakeholders are presented in the Annexes of this report with consent from their respective owners.

NET-Fuels Concept/Partners/Expected Results

ALMA MATER STUDIORUM - UNIVERSITA' DI BOLOGNA

Andrea Contin

8-9 November, 2013

Terrassa, Spain

Funded by the
European Union

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NET-Fuels objectives

The NET-Fuels project will produce **carbon-negative bio and synthetic fuels**:

- with maximum biomass utilization efficiency
- from a wide range of low-quality and low-cost feedstocks
- using an integrated prototype with auxiliary systems combining key-technologies for carbon-negative fuel production

NET-Fuels will deliver:

- a) a **thermochemical process** with post-reforming to produce a hydrogen-rich syngas, a biooil with superior physical and chemical properties than traditional fast pyrolysis oil and a high-quality biochar;
- b) a **hydrogen separation step** to generate a green hydrogen stream;
- c) an oxy-fuel combustion (or oxy-combustion) of the tail gas after H₂ separation to produce a CO₂-rich exhaust;
- d) a **bio-electro-chemical system** for methane production from CO₂;
- e) an **application to soil of the biochar** to achieve certified negative greenhouse gases (GHG) emissions (carbon sink).

These results will be accompanied by new datasets addressing environmental and socio-economic issues and a prospective study to exploit the results to be used in multiple value chains.

NET-Fuels in a nutshell

Partners

<p>ALMA MATER STUDIORUM UNIVERSITÀ DI BOLOGNA</p>	<p>Coordination Life-cycle thinking/system analysis, social science applications Risks</p>
	<p>TCR technology, PSA unit for H₂ separation, oxyfuel combustion chamber construction, CO₂ compression & filling station, heat transfer unit from oxyfuel combustion to the TCR unit</p>
	<p>BioElectroMethanation (BEM) reactor development, test, construction and operation</p>
	<p>Life-cycle assessment, oxyfuel combustion chamber, heat transfer design</p>
	<p>Biochar application in field trials, carbon sink certification</p>
	<p>Business development, exploitation, potential industrial scale-up</p>
	<p>Dissemination and communication</p>

TCR[®]

The 30 kg/h TCR[®] at Fraunhofer UMSICHT, Sulzbach-Rosenberg will be equipped with the PSA and the Oxyfuel combustion

BioElectroMethanation

A BEM pilot reactor with treatment capacity of 50 L- CO_2 /day will be built

Mass and energy balance

Efficiency = fraction of the input energy which goes into fuels = **55÷63%**

With the present carbon intensity of electricity:
- 80 g CO_{2e} / MJ

In 2030: **- 105 g CO_{2eq} / MJ**

Impacts

DESTINATION: Sustainable Secure and competitive energy supply

Fostering the European global leadership in affordable, secure and sustainable renewable energy technologies

Energy systems, grids and storage

Carbon capture, utilisation and storage (CCUS)

Impacts

**With Biomass availability of
200-350 Mt/year**

**NET-Fuels will ensure 145 ± 55 Mt/year of
CO₂ sequestration**

**NET-Fuels will ensure 110 ± 50 Mt/year of
NET negative emissions**

**NET-Fuels will produce 110 ± 50 Mtoe/year of
Advanced Bio-Fuels in 2030**

**NET-Fuels will cover a share of $6.7 \pm 2.5\%$ of
total transport fuel consumption in 2030**

Sustainability

Conduct a Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) of GHG emissions

The objective is to implement a dynamic model to compute dynamic GHGs emissions of the integrated process, with the aim of validating the negative emissions over time and under different conditions

Development of a C-sink certification guideline for the NET-Fuels process

The objective is to enable the certification of the net negative emissions generated by the NET-Fuels process with reasonable effort and cost

Validation of the suitability of TCR-char as a soil amendment

The objective is to record, calculate and certify the negative emissions generated by the production of biochar and its application to soil at TRL5, to produce a certification assessment format to support tradable negative emission / C-sink certificates

Social systems, Policy and Acceptability

Impacts on social systems and policy

The objective is to connect Net-Fuel product system to all supply products and to corresponding sectors and uses, aggregating regional data and sectors, and defining the limits of the industrial expansion against the potential availability of residual biomass

Industrial system applications and business potential

The objective is to validate the overall integrated system and approach of the project and to address the project's Business Development for a future commercial phase, as well as its Regulatory Assessment

Acceptability

The objective is to increase the acceptability of the biofuels through a qualitative study of cultural and political dimensions

Work Packages

Thank you for your attention

<https://netfuelsproject.org>

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01

Fraunhofer Institute for Environmental, Safety and Energy Technology UMSICHT

Fraunhofer UMSICHT - Pioneer for a sustainable world

By developing new technologies, we contribute to solving major challenges such as climate change, energy supply and raw material security.

Fraunhofer UMSICHT

Institute for Environmental, Safety, and Energy Technology

Oberhausen / North-Rhine
Westphalia

Sulzbach-Rosenberg / Bavaria

- **7th largest** Fraunhofer Institute
- **622** Employees
- Operating budget 2022: **78 million €**

Fraunhofer UMSICHT – Focus of our activities

Research fields, technologies and industry services

Carbon Management

Circular Economy

Local Energy Systems

Green Hydrogen

Sulzbach-Rosenberg institute branch at a glance

Advanced Carbon
Conversion
Technologies

Clean Combustion
and Process Heat

Secondary Resources
and Assessment

FACTS

100 Employees

2100 m² Workshop

10 Mio. EUR Turnover

SERVICES

Process and plant development

Laboratory and analytics

Waste and resource strategies

Technology assessment and LCA

02

Carbon Dioxide Removal

IPCC Report

Climate scenarios

Basically all scenarios that limit warming to 2°C in 2100 include negative emissions.

CO₂ emissions for SSP-based scenarios and C1-C8 categories

Temperature for SSP-based scenarios over the 21st century and C1-C8 at 2100

https://report.ipcc.ch/ar6syr/pdf/IPCC_AR6_SYR_LongerReport.pdf, entnommen am 31.03.2023

Anthropogenic global warming

Negative Emission

The need for negative emissions increases significantly with the residual budget of positive emissions.

<https://www.cicero.oslo.no/en/articles/stylised-pathways-to-well-below-2c>, 4.9.2018, entnommen 31.03.2023

Negative Emission Technologies

An Overview and Storage Location

[1] Technical Summary IPCC AR6 WG III, 2022

[2] https://www.wissenschaftsplattform-klimaschutz.de/files/WPKS_Gutachten_MCC_PIK.pdf

Modified European Biochar Industry graphic, inspired by (SRU, 2020)

Negative Emission Technologies

An Overview and Storage Location

[1] Technical Summary IPCC AR6 WG III, 2022

[2] https://www.wissenschaftsplattform-klimaschutz.de/files/WPKS_Gutachten_MCC_PIK.pdf

Modified European Biochar Industry graphic, inspired by (SRU, 2020)

Our vision

Efficient combination of BECCS/U and PyCCS/U

03

Thermo Catalytic Reforming (TCR) Technology

Sustainable carbon from biomass

The TCR[®]-Technology
Sustainable hydrocarbons from
biogenic residues

TCR - Functional principle

Intermediate pyrolysis with integrated catalytic reforming step

First stage: biomass is broken down into carbonisate and volatile components in a continuously operating auger reactor at medium temperatures (< 500 °Celsius). The formation of tar and other pollutants is prevented by optimized process conditions in the various reactor zones.

Second stage: In a post-reformer, the carbonisate and vapors are **catalytically refined to improve gas yield and product quality**. The vapors are then cooled. During condensation, oil and process water are separated. The remaining gas is cleaned.

TCR - Functional principle

Intermediate pyrolysis with integrated catalytic reforming step

Use cases and outcome

- Utilization of biogenic residues
- Decentralised application possible
- Products with near-zero carbon footprint

Products

- Syngas with up to 50 % green hydrogen
- Oil with high thermal stability for processing into standard fuels
- Coal for soil application / storage / energetic use

TCR - Feedstocks

High potential of input materials

- Variable biomass, biogenic residues, bio-waste and mixtures (>70% DM) can be used as feedstock
- More than **90 biogenic waste materials** already tested
- **Examples:**
 - Agricultural residues
 - Digestate
 - Sewage sludge
 - Spent grains
 - Paper residues
 - Leaves
 - Biowaste
 - ...

TCR - Products

Thermal stability of TCR-Oil opens the path for hydrotreatment

TCR – Technical Evolution

Lab and pilot scale units

Lab scale unit 2kg / h

Pilot scale unit 30kg / h

Product gas treatment

- Cyclone
- Filter
- Condensation
- Electrostatic precipitator
- Scrubber

PSA- H₂ Separation

- up to 250 Nm³/h raw gas
- 10 bar
- 4 Columns

HDO - Hydrogenation

- 30 l/h
- 110 bar
- 360-400°C

CHP-Unit dual fuel

- 220 kW_{el}
- 350 kW_{th}

Pyrolyzer - TCR

- 500 kg/h

Workshop Hohenburg

Green crude from sewage sludge

TCR – Technology

Summary

- Utilization of local biogenic residues for sustainable fuels
- Decentralized plant technology for optimized feedstock usage
- High flexibility on input material
- CO₂-neutral, respectively CO₂-negative products / energy carriers
- H₂ rich synthesis gas
- Carbonisate to be used for soil applications or sequestration

Further reading on TCR Technology

https://www.umsicht-suro.fraunhofer.de/en/Our_Solution/tcr-technology.html

Information on Next Generation Biofuels

https://www.umsicht-suro.fraunhofer.de/en/Our_Solution/biofuels.html

04

Oxycombustion

Our vision

Efficient combination of BECCS/U and PyCCS/U

Oxycombustion of biogenic gaseous

Overview

Oxycombustion of biogenic gaseous

Overview

- Cheap and easy carbon capture, as far as oxygen is available
- Flexible use of various biogenic gases as a fuel
 - Pyrolysis gas
 - Biogas
 - gasification (except for air as gasification agent)
- Design of testing environment
- Combustion heat output of 50 kW
- CO₂ purity in the exhaust gas of >95% through primary measures
- Flameless-combustion

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Fraunhofer Institute for
Environmental, Safety and Energy
Technology UMSICHT

**Thank you very much for your
attention**

Increasing biomass conversion efficiency to carbon-negative sustainable biofuels by combination of thermal and bio-electrochemical processes

Presentation of the NET Fuels Technologies: bioelectrochemical methanation

Daniele Molognoni, Simone Colantoni, Maria Vega, Eduard Borrás

NET-Fuels 1st Stakeholders Community Workshop -
Leitat (Terrassa, Barcelona, Spain)

9 November 2023

General information

- **Anode (abiotic)**

(+0.82 V vs SHE)

- **Cathode** **Electrotrophs**

(-0.24 V vs SHE)

(-0.41 V vs SHE)

General information

- Electroactive microorganisms: *Geobacter sulfurreducens*, *Shewanella oneidensis*
- Present in aerobic and anaerobic **activated sludge**, riverbed sediments, etc.
- Colonize the electrode(s) in form of **biofilm** (attached biomass)
- **Biological catalyst** (of OX and/or RED)

Do not distribute without permission

$$E_{\text{cell}} > 1.23\text{V} (\sim 1.5\text{-}2\text{V})$$

Confidential

Slide 3

METHANOGENESIS + MET = Bioelectrochemical methanation (BEM)

(Geppert et al., 2016)

Comparison of BEM with other methanogenesis technologies

(A) Bioelectrochemical methanation

(B) Chemical methanation

(C) Biological methanation

Power to gas/fuel (P2G)

(Mirzoyan et al., 2010)

Parameters	(A) laboratory-stage BEM	(B) pilot-stage Chemical methanation	(C) pilot-stage Biological methanation
CH ₄ production rate (m ³ CH ₄ m ⁻³ reactor d ⁻¹)	0.27 – 27	1500 m ³ CH ₄ m ⁻³ catalyst d ⁻¹	1.2 – 43.2
Conversion efficiency (%)	65 – 99%	46-75%	58%
Energy consumption (kWh m ⁻³ CH ₄)	11 – 19	26 – 35	19
CH ₄ purity (%)	≥ 95 %	≥ 96 %	98 – 99 %
Operating pressure (bar)	1	1-100	1 – 4
Operating temperature (°C)	20-30	180-600	40 – 70
Observations	On-demand ignition	Expensive catalysts	On-site need of H ₂

BEM optimization

- **How to improve BEM?** → **development of highly selective and efficient biocathodes & optimized process engineering**
 - Hollow fibers membrane contactors for efficient CO_2 delivery system in the aqueous catholyte medium
 - Selection of cathode material with high EMG performances and biological compatibility
 - Development of highly performing biofilm on the cathode material (highly active inoculum, optimized inoculation procedure)
 - Optimization of applied voltage and cathode chamber configuration/design for minimal residual H_2/CO_2 in the outflow
 - Optimize ratio between electrode surface and volume (m^2/m^3)
 - Fine-tuned dimensioning and control of the process (flow speed, recirculation, etc.) to minimize excess CO_2 present in the outflow

CO₂ absorption in cathode electrolyte

CO₂ absorption background

- The absorption of CO₂ through membranes involves the selective separation of this gas using a **semipermeable membrane**. This membrane allows the **preferential passage of CO₂** over other gases, facilitating its capture.

Electrodes characteristics

- High conductivity ($\rho < 1 \Omega \text{ cm}$)
- **Stability** (no sacrificial electrode)
- Resistance to corrosion
- **Biocompatibility**
- **Specific surface** $> 0.3 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$
- Porosity $> 90\%$, $\Phi_{\text{porous}} > 10 \mu\text{m}$
- **Mechanical strength**
- Positively charged surface
- **Hydrophilicity** (contact angle $< 90^\circ$)
- Cheap, recyclable materials

Fuel Cell Earth

(Wei et al., 2011)

Reactor architectures for BEM

- Double chamber reactors: H cells

Double chamber reactors: Flat-plate

(Leitat image, not published, confidential)

- Other double chamber reactor configurations:

Moving bed reactor:

- Anolite working V = 1 L
- Catholite working V = 4.5 L

(Enzman et al., 2019)

(Cai et al., 2022)

Tubular type:

- Anolite working V = 145 L
- Catholite working V = 50 L

The BEM process in Net-Fuels

Thank you for your attention
Any questions?

Funded by the European Union (Grant N° 1101083780). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. The European Union cannot be held responsible for them.

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Biofuels and derivatives projects in the current Oil & Gas industry

Promoting efficient and sustainable use of bioenergy

2023

Our cluster

The Bioenergy Cluster of Catalonia brings together the bioenergy business sector and works to promote energy projects that ensure the transformation of the country towards a competitive and circular economic model.

Who we are

CBC integrates over 100 companies and entities from the private sector and public sector.

Main Bioenergy Cluster in South Europe

Our value chain:

Engineering

Research and innovation

Production of biomass

Production of biogas

Biomass machinery and equipment

Biogas machinery and equipment

Final user

Public administrations

Mission

CBC aims to promote the sustainable and efficient use of bioenergy, while enhancing competitiveness through overall value chain and contributing to the economic competitiveness, sustainability and welfare of Catalonia.

Integrates 2 Working Groups that promote business collaboration to solve the main challenges of our sector, by promoting strategic projects, actions or activities.

Biomass Working Group

Jordi Tarradas
Boscat Fusta
gerentboscat@boscat.cat

Biogas Working Group

Màrius Aguirre
Envolta Energia
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Services

- Business development
- Connections and collaborations
- Visibility and promotion
- Representation
- Support in the development of projects
- Training and recruitment
- Innovation and technology transfer

Who we are

Production and Distribution of biomass

Production and Distribution of Biogas

Biomass machinery and equipment

Biogas machinery and equipment

Who we are

Research and Innovation

Transversal Services

Clients

Third sector

Public Administration

Engineering and Energy Services

Innovation, Consulting, Engineering & Outsourcing.

We help our customers
become more competitive.

Our Mission. To provide innovative and technological solutions to make our customers more effective and competitive.

Our Vision. To be the company where engineers love to work, transforming ideas into progress & success. A trustworthy partner for our customers

Our Values

Engineering
Enthusiast

We walk
the talk

Moving forward
together

Challenge
seekers

Our attributes

Enthusiast
Expert

Brave
Driven

Reliable
Consistent

Near
Empathic

Positioning

An international engineering company eager to help its clients succeed in their technological projects. Every day, our engineers work side by side with customers in all engineering activities across the product lifecycle. Each one of them thrives to understand client needs, and provide solutions while maintaining an easy and enjoyable customer experience.

At CT, we enjoy helping clients achieve their goals, and see barriers as opportunities. We are engineers that love engineering challenges.

We are engineers
that love **engineering**
challenges.

4 Keys of success

E-fuel

- Petrol or Diesel: C_xH_y
- E-fuels:

Fuente: efuel-today

Cómo funciona una planta de combustibles sintéticos cero emisiones

Fuente: Repsol

Biofuel

Biofuels are a promising source of renewable energy, but using biomass for energy is nothing new – at the most basic level, humans have been using biomass for energy since prehistoric times.

Technically, a 'biofuel' is any biomass that has been converted into fuel. This can include bioethanol and algal biodiesel, but it can also include firewood, charcoal, and animal dung.

First-Generation Biofuels

Generally, first-generation biofuels are fuels derived from food crops like corn and sugarcane. These fuels took off throughout the 20th century. During World War II, vegetable oil was used to replace petroleum. Later on, the oil embargo of the 1970s motivated greater investment in biofuels.

One persistent issue with first-gen biofuels is that they compete with food crops for land and resources. As of 2021, 40% of corn went to bioethanol production despite producing only 5% of the nation's energy needs. In response, researchers have sought alternative biomass sources.

Modern Second-Generation Biofuels

Second-generation biofuels are associated with inedible vegetation, usually cellulosic crops (woody or grass-like plants), or residues from agriculture and forestry.

As they don't use food crops directly, these fuels are supposed to reduce competition between energy and food needs. However, their real impact may be more complex – for example, some second-generation biomass types provide food for livestock, while others require a significant amount of water.

Some growing operations may also contribute to land degradation and deforestation. Moreover, processing cellulosic crops into fuel involves more energy, water, and processing.

Modern Third-Generation Biofuels

Third-generation biofuels are associated with algal biomass.

Algae are a promising biomass alternative as they multiply rapidly and remove large amounts of CO₂ from the atmosphere.

While they aren't very energy-dense, making current algal biofuel processing fairly inefficient, there is ongoing research into engineering new kinds of algae.

Waste-Based Biomass Fuels

Several other processes generate materials that also provide a source of fuel. For example, decomposition in landfills produces methane-rich gases that can be combusted for energy.

Similarly, decomposition in wastewater can be used to produce energy, or reactors that decompose organic matter (anaerobic digesters) can be specifically designed for fuel production.

Solid waste can also be incinerated in waste-to-energy plants.

Biofuel - Bioetanol

Fuente: Vertex - Ecocarburantes

Biofuel - Biometano

Fuente: Nippon Gases

Biofuel - Biometano

Climate & Energy | Fuel | Grid & Infrastructure | Exploration & Production | Refining

Spain's Cepsa targets up to 15 biomethane plants by 2030

Reuters

October 16, 2023 2:18 PM GMT+2 · Updated 19 days ago

A view from a ferry shows the refinery of Cepsa at Cepsa Energy Park in San Roque, near Algeciras, Spain January 19, 2023. REUTERS/Jon Nazca/Photo Acquire Licenses/Reuters

Repsol, Naturgy, and Reganosa collaborate with Impulsa Galicia to transform waste into biomethane and organic fertilizers

Press Release · 28/09/2022 11:00 · 4 min

Spain: Biomethane investments versus green hydrogens

Nieuwsbericht | 13-02-2023 | 12:00

“Biomethane is one of the most attractive segments of the energy transition for investors,” was the message sent to the market by Goldman Sachs just a few days ago. The firm has launched its newly formed Verdalia Bioenergy in Spain as part of its commitment to biomethane.

SEP 29, 2023

Naturgy to build its sixth biomethane plant in Spain

Naturgy is set to build its sixth biomethane production plant in Spain and the first in Andalusia in the municipality of Utrera (Seville).

The plant will be built in collaboration with KEPLER Engineering and Ecogestion, and is scheduled to begin operation in 2025.

The Utrera project, which currently in administrative processing, will be one of the largest in Naturgy's portfolio, with an annual production capacity of 40 GWh of biomethane, potentially supplying more than 10,500 Andalusian homes.

Biofuel - Biometano

Spain: new platform will allow construction of at least 10 biomethane plants by 2030

Enagás Renewable and Genia Bioenergy announced the creation of a joint venture 'The Green Vector' (TGV), a platform to promote the development of biomethane from organic waste in Spain. The initiative integrates all the actors in the waste recovery chain, including the production, distribution and final consumption of biomethane.

This project, which aims to promote decarbonization, the circular economy and the reduction of energy dependence, is in line with the Biogas Roadmap of the Government of Spain, the Integrated Strategic Energy and Climate Plan (PNIEC), the National Air Pollution Control Program (PNCCA), and the European goals set by the REPowerEU Plan and the European Energy and Environment Framework 2030.

Redexis, Inerco plan 10 biomethane plants in Spain

Gas Renewables 28 Jun 2023 12:20

m+

[RACHAEL BURNETT](#)

Madrid

28 Jun 2023 12:20

(Montel) Spanish gas firm Redexis has partnered with industrial development company Inerco to develop 10 biomethane plants in Spain which would inject a total of 500 GWh/year into the grid.

Verdalia Bioenergy launches business in Spain with Spanish portfolio purchase

Renewable energy

Entrepreneurship

Sustainability

Biofuel - Biometano

News and Media

GOLDMAN SACHS ASSET MANAGEMENT TO LAUNCH VERDALIA BIOENERGY WITH THE AIM TO INVEST IN EXCESS OF €1 BILLION IN THE EUROPEAN BIOMETHANE SECTOR

February 6, 2023 | 4 Minute Read

Swiss company Axpo buys 40% stake in Torre Santamaría to boost biomethane production

Renewable energy

Innovation

X in

Press Release

Macquarie Asset Management's Green Investment Group launches VORN Bioenergy

London, 28 February 2023

Biofuel - Biometano

Número de plantas
propuestas de biometano
por tipología por CC.AA.

Fuente: análisis de PwC y Biovic

CC.AA.	Número de plantas Agro + EDAR + RSU	Número de plantas de Cultivos intermedios	Número de plantas de Biomasa forestal residual	Número de plantas totales
Castilla y León	271	215	34	520
Andalucía	255	59	20	334
Castilla-La Mancha	208	88	9	305
Cataluña	212	28	8	248
Aragón	140	83	15	238
Extremadura	94	54	18	164
Galicia	92	18	11	121
Comunidad Valenciana	95	8	3	106
Navarra	38	21	5	62
País Vasco	29	5	7	41
Murcia	31	6	3	40
Comunidad de Madrid	19	9	3	31
Principado de Asturias	23	2	2	27
Islas Baleares	18	5	4	25
Islas Canarias	18	2	5	23
Cantabria	18	1	4	21
La Rioja	13	5	2	20
TOTAL	1.566	609	151	2.326

Fuente: Sedigas, PwC & Biovic

Biofuel

 At Urbaser, we work on the treatment and recovery of MARPOL waste from Annex I: hydrocarbon waste present in engine room bilges or from fuel purification machines and motor oil.

- Alfaro (La Rioja)
- Fuenlabrada (Madrid)
- Cartagena (Murcia)
- Palos de la Frontera (Huelva)

We obtain a recycled fuel that can then be introduced back into the market. This way, we reduce abusive fossil fuel consumption and the environmental effects that entails.

Current projects

Repsol se une a Enerkem y Agbar para construir una planta de valorización de residuos en Tarragona

Noticia química - 27/04/2021

- Repsol, Enerkem y Agbar construirán la primera planta de la Península Ibérica que transformará residuos en productos de la química derivada.
- La planta tendrá capacidad para convertir unas 400.000 toneladas de residuos sólidos urbanos no reciclables en aproximadamente 220.000 toneladas anuales de metanol que se transformará en plásticos renovables o biocombustibles avanzados.
- Se empleará una tecnología pionera en su campo, que permitirá reducir las emisiones de CO₂ en unas 200.000 toneladas anuales.

La refinería de Repsol en A Coruña fabrica biocombustible con aceite de cocina usado

Notas de prensa · 20/10/2021 00:00 · 5 min de lectura

- Repsol incrementa su capacidad de producción de diésel renovable a partir de residuos con el procesado en el complejo coruñés de 500 toneladas de aceite de fritura de origen nacional como materia prima.
- La refinería de A Coruña tiene una producción consolidada de combustibles de baja huella de carbono, a la que se suma esta nueva tipología de biocombustible, impulsando la economía circular para alcanzar el objetivo de cero emisiones netas en el año 2050.
- El uso de hidrobiodiésel en vehículos supone una reducción de hasta el 90% de las emisiones de CO₂ respecto a las de un gasóleo mineral.

Current projects

Biocombustible Avanzado

REPSOL Con una inversión de 188 millones de euros

REPSOL CONSTRUIRÁ EN CARTAGENA LA PRIMERA PLANTA DE BIOCMBUSTIBLES AVANZADOS DE ESPAÑA

Inversión en Cartagena

188 Millones de euros

Reducción de emisiones gracias al uso de materias primas recicladas

900 Mil toneladas de CO₂

Inicio previsto de la producción

2023

Huelva

Centro petrolero/químico de Andalucía en el puerto de Huelva.

Modernización de la tecnología para poder incluir el procesamiento de aceite de cocina y ácidos grasos en la producción de biocombustible. (10M€)

Berantevilla

Planta capaz de procesar varias materias primas, incluyendo aceite de cocina usado, ácidos grasos, sebo y otros residuos. Al estar alineada con la Directiva de Energías Renovables (REDII) puede producir biocombustible conforme a la norma EN14214. (10M€)

Current projects

Biocombustible para aviones

Repsol produce en Tarragona biocombustible para aviones

📄 Notas de prensa · 21/01/2021 18:00 · 4 min de lectura

- Repsol ha producido en su Complejo Industrial de Tarragona un lote de biojet, un combustible sostenible para la aviación, el segundo de este tipo en España.
- Compuesto por **10.000 toneladas de combustible con componente bio para aviación**, el lote supondrá que se **evite la emisión de 630 toneladas de CO₂ a la atmósfera**, equivalente a 55 vuelos Madrid-Barcelona.

Repsol produce por primera vez en España biocombustible para aviación a partir de residuos

📄 Notas de prensa · 25/08/2021 00:00 · 4 min de lectura

Repsol ha producido en su Complejo Industrial de Petronor, en Bilbao, el **primer lote de biojet en España obtenido a partir de residuos**, un combustible sostenible para la aviación.

El **lote** consta de **5.300 toneladas** de combustible sostenible cuyo uso supondrá que se **evite la emisión a la atmósfera de 300 toneladas de CO₂**, el equivalente a 40 vuelos Madrid-Bilbao.

Repsol produce por primera vez en España biocombustible para aviones

📄 Notas de prensa · 03/08/2020 17:50 · 4 min de lectura

- Repsol ha producido en su Complejo Industrial de Puertollano el primer lote de biojet del mercado español, por lo que se convierte en la compañía pionera en la fabricación en España de este combustible sostenible para la aviación.
- El **primer lote consta de 7.000 toneladas de combustible para aviación con componente bio**, cuyo uso supondrá que **se evite la emisión a la atmósfera de 440 toneladas de CO₂**, el equivalente a 40 vuelos Madrid-Barcelona.

Current projects

Gas a partir de residuos

Petronor

Planta de generación de gas a partir de residuos urbanos y podrá procesar cerca de 10.000 toneladas al año; capacidad que podrá ampliarse en fases posteriores hasta 100.000 toneladas al año, equivalente a todos los residuos urbanos del entorno (2024, 20 M€).

La planta de pirólisis contribuirá a la descarbonización de la refinería

Current projects

H₂ renewable

bp, Iberdrola y Enagás estudian el desarrollo del mayor proyecto de hidrógeno verde en la Comunidad Valenciana

- Este proyecto se ubicaría en la refinería de bp en Castellón, donde se construiría un electrolizador de 20 megavatios (MW), alimentado con energía renovable producida, entre otras fuentes de generación, por una planta fotovoltaica de 40 MW.
- En fases posteriores, la capacidad de electrólisis podría incrementarse hasta 115 MW, que la convertiría en el mayor proyecto de hidrógeno del sector de refino en España.
- Este proyecto reduciría las emisiones de la refinería en hasta 24.000 toneladas de CO₂ al año, contribuyendo a la descarbonización del corredor industrial de la región.

Petronor instala un electrolizador por 8,9 millones como primer paso del Corredor Vasco del Hidrógeno

Este hidrógeno renovable se destinará a los primeros autobuses y vehículos ligeros en una plataforma logística de movilidad

BILBAO, 20 Sep. (EUROPA PRESS) - Petronor contará en el segundo semestre del año 2022 con un electrolizador de 2,5 MW, que supondrá una inversión de 8,9 millones de euros y será "el primer paso" hacia un Corredor Vasco del Hidrógeno. Este primer hidrógeno renovable en Euskadi se destinará a los primeros autobuses y vehículos ligeros en una plataforma logística de movilidad, que contará con una primera hidrogenadora de Euskadi, impulsada por el EVE y Repsol.

SHyrius convertirá a la Región en uno de los valles de hidrógeno verde más relevantes de Europa

Reto · La firma, junto a Enagás Renovable y Repsol, han formado un consorcio para construir un electrolizador de 100 MW de capacidad en Cartagena

Cepsa y Fertiberia firman una alianza estratégica para impulsar la producción de hidrógeno verde y descarbonizar la industria en Huelva

Con esta unión, Cepsa y Fertiberia se convierten en socios estratégicos del proyecto para desarrollar 1 GW de capacidad de electrólisis en Patos de la Frontera, en el marco del Valle Andaluz del Hidrógeno Verde. Este valle contará con una capacidad de 2 GW –1 GW en el Campo de Gibraltar (Cádiz) y otro en Patos de la Frontera (Huelva)- y una producción de hasta 300.000 toneladas, en los Parques Energéticos de Cepsa,

Contact us

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SPAIN

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- Vigo
- Ferrol
- Sabadell
- Cartagena

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- Vitrolles
- Nantes
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- Paris
- Rochefort
- Bordeaux

GERMANY

- Hamburg
- Munich

PORTUGAL

- Lisbon
- Porto

UK

- Bristol

INDIA

- Bangalore

BRAZIL

- Rio de Janeiro

Thanks for your attention. More info here:

www.thectengineeringgroup.com

ENGINEERING
DRIVEN
PEOPLE

Thank *you.*

SEMPRE-BIO

SEMPRE-BIO

**SEcuring doMestic PRoduction of cost-Effective
BIOmethane**

PM: Alejandra Córdova V.

CETAQUA
CENTRO TECNOLÓGICO DEL AGUA

**Funded by
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Pioneering public-private partnership model

Main activities

1. R&D

Water resource management

Environmental, economic and social sustainability

Critical infrastructure management and resilience

Water 4.0

Biofactory and resource recovery

2. KNOWLEDGE-BASED SERVICES

3. DIGITAL SERVICES

SEMPRE-BIO at glance

Goals

1. Demonstrate novel and cost-effective biomethane production solutions and pathways.
1. Increase the market up-take of biomethane related technologies.
1. Support circular economy.
1. Reduce dependence on fossil fuels.

Numbers

42
Months

16
Partners

6
Countries

9.9M
Funding

Locations

European Biomethane Innovation Ecosystem

Case Study I: Baix Llobregat (Spain)

Feedstock

Technology

Site

Final use of biomethane

Wastewater

CO²
Biomethanation

Electrolysis

Case Study 1:
El Prat de Llobregat (ES)

Compression to CNG
for public transportation

Case Study 2: Bourges (France)

Feedstock

Green waste from the city of Bourges

Technology

Pyrolysis

CO
Methanation

Site

Case Study 2:
Bourges (FR)

Final use of biomethane

Grid injection

Case Study 3: Adinkerke (Belgium)

Feedstock

Cattle manure and organic biological waste as co-substrate

Technology

Cryo separation

Site

Case Study 3:
TBD (BE)

Final use of biomethane

Stored locally

Work packages

WP4 – Advanced technologies for efficient valorization of CO₂ from biomethane streams

WP2 – Biomethane Production Technologies for Greenfield Scenarios

WP3 – Integrating Biomethane Upgrading Technology in Downscaling and Retrofitting Scenarios

WP5 – Economic Assessment & Market Uptake

WP6 – Connect, Communicate, Exploit, Replicate

WP7 – Project Management

WP1 – European Biomethane Innovation Ecosystems

SEMPRE-BIO Activities

Nov. 2022

Kickoff Meeting

Barcelona, ES.

Mar. 2023

Workshop WP5

París, FR.

May. 2023

Ist General Assembly

Online meeting.

Nov. 15th 2023

Ist Webinar

Barcelona, ES.

Evento híbrido

Nov. 2023

2nd General Assembly

Leipzig, DEU.

Funded by
the European Union

SEMPRE-BIO Advance

Expected outcomes

- 01** Increase the cost-effectiveness of conversion in biomethane production.
- 02** Diversify conversion technologies for biomethane.
- 03** Contribute to the acceptance of biomethane technologies in the gas market.
- 04** Contribute to the demonstration on a semi-industrial scale of new conversion technologies to produce biomethane from wastewater, wood biomass and manure.

Expected impacts

Biomethane as a substitute for imported LNG.

Biomethane as a fuel substitute in transportation.

Reduction of CO₂ by 213 million tons/year by 2050.

Diversify energy sources and new routes.

Reduce the need for strategic reserves.

Smaller extension of critical infrastructure to protect.

¡Thank you for your attention!

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Funded by
the European Union

The REGENERA project:

Development of hybrid energy storage technologies and predictive models to transform industries into decentralized points for renewable energy management

Plan de
Recuperación,
Transformación
y Resiliencia

Financiado por
la Unión Europea
NextGenerationEU

Introduction

1

Objectives and Scope of the Project

2

Hybrid Storage Technologies

3

Predictive Models and RE Management

4

Current Status of the Project

5

Conclusions

6

Introduction

1

Objectives and Scope of the Project

2

Hybrid Storage Technologies

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Energy from renewable sources is expected to grow **from the current 25% to 86% in 2050**, promoting sustainable development. However, this forecast entails multiple challenges due to the variable nature of renewable energies, so energy systems worldwide must adapt to ensure the energy supply.

UN definition of *Sustainability*:

“Meeting the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs”

To achieve these objectives, it will be necessary to integrate **energy storage and energy resources optimization systems.**

The REGENERA project investigates the **distributed electricity storage from renewable energy surplus** converting it in green fuels as hydrogen, methane and hythane.

These technologies are tested in different industrial facilities, using their waste streams (wastewater or CO₂) to produce the green fuels and the project development extends until 2024.

It is focused on two main strategies:

1. Power-to-Gas approach for the long period storage of large quantities of electricity.
2. Energy management optimization system that allows coupling industries energy demand with RE production.

Energy optimization predictive models

Introduction

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Objectives and Scope of the Project

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REGENERA is being developed by a consortium of 8 companies and many other external collaborators.

For this Project, 3 main objectives have been set, focused on researching innovative technologies to efficiently and economically store RE surplus:

1. Cost reduction of the storage of renewable energy surplus by **33%**.
2. Cost reduction of the green fuels (H₂ and CH₄) production by **35%**.
3. Reduction on the industries CO₂ emissions by **25%**.

In addition, 3 pilots will be built in industrial locations (WWTP and brewing industry) to obtain information about the scalation of the technologies and allow a validation to TRL5.

For the efficient storage of the RE surplus, research into predictive energy management models is done in REGENERA.

Introduction

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Objectives and Scope of the Project

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Three technologies were selected for the development of the project because they are especially suitable for working decentralized and adapted to the fluctuations of the renewable energies.

H ₂ production by electrolysis	BioCH ₄ production	Hythane production (CH ₄ / H ₂)
Solid Oxide Electrolysis (SOEL) coupled to a water purification system that allows to operate with wastewater.	Bioelectrochemical reactor (BES-EMG) fed with wastewater and a CO ₂ rich stream.	Alkaline scrubber for biogas purification and a BES reactor for the generation of H ₂ (BES-BioH ₂).

Introduction

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Objectives and Scope of the Project

2

Hybrid Storage Technologies

3

Predictive Models and RE Management

4

Current Status of the Project

5

Conclusions

6

For the optimal operation of the mentioned technologies, it is crucial to implement an energy management system. This system must allow to:

- Coupling between industrial processes and renewable energy production, to maximize energy use / storage.
- Select the optimal operation mode to work as efficiently as possible.
- Control and monitor the results obtained.

In REGENERA, the aim is for industries to become **prosumers** for the delocalized management of renewable energies.

Specifically, work will be done on Machine Learning algorithms that allow to anticipate future consumption situations together with a Digital Operation Platform (PDO).

Figura 6. Gráfica ensayo 5. MAE: 0.78 kWh

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The main milestones achieved to date are summarized below:

1. Laboratory prototype phase of the different technologies has been completed.
2. Industrial pilots are being developed. This pilots will be tested in the WWTP and brewing industry.
3. The Big Data module for data collection and subsequent predictive algorithm treatment has been implemented.

The next steps for the coming year until the end of REGENERA would consist of:

1. Erection and commissioning of the pilots on-site.
2. Testing of the technologies in a relevant industrial environment.
3. Analysis of results and calibration of predictive model

Introduction

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Objectives and Scope of the Project

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Hybrid Storage Technologies

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The REGENERA project is completely aligned with promoting safe, efficient and clean energy for the 21st century:

It promotes the decarbonization of the Spanish economy to drastically reduce GHG emissions

Reduce energy dependence on fossil fuels

R&D in renewable and sustainable energies

THANK YOU

www.engie.es

<https://www.linkedin.com/company/engie-españa/>

Indoor CO₂ as renewable carbon source: Coupling indoor CO₂ direct air capture to microbial electrosynthesis technologies

Luis R. López de León

Alba Cabrera-Codony, Paolo Dessì, Silvia Bolognesi
Pau Zamora, Irene Soler, Joan Bermejo, Kieran Jiménez, Ilías Azzouzi,
Guillem Alonso, Arnau Ponce, Ricard Darnés, Mireia Serrat
Bart Kraakman, Dolors Balaguer, Sebastià Puig

Terrassa, November 9th, 2023

Presentation content

- **Research Motivation**
 - CO₂ Direct Air Capture (CO₂-DAC)
 - Sources of indoor CO₂
 - Types of indoor environments
 - Mitigation strategies
- **Case Study: “The MICRO-BIO process”**
 - CO₂ concentrator module
 - Microbial Electrosynthesis module
 - Capillary microbioreactor module
- **Next steps and summary**

Research Motivation

Sources of renewable energy and renewable carbon

Source: <http://nova-institute.eu/>

Research Motivation

Sources of renewable energy and renewable carbon

Source: <http://nova-institute.eu/>

Capture and bioconversion of CO₂ from indoor environments

Sources of renewable carbon

CO₂ Indoor Direct Air Capture (CO₂-DAC)

The CO₂ present in indoor environments represents a potential/unexplored source of renewable carbon

Sources of emission of CO₂ in indoor environments

Human metabolism

Combustion and tobacco smoke

Engine emissions/instrumentation

Outdoor air infiltration

Representative indoor environments

School classrooms

Recommended value
1000-1500 ppm_v < CO₂

Average values
3200-5800 ppm_v CO₂

Office buildings

Recommended value
1000-1500 ppm_v < CO₂

Average values
850-1300 ppm_v CO₂

Metro cabins

Recommended value
1000-1500 ppm_v < CO₂

Average values
650 and 5525 ppm_v CO₂

Indoor environments with low “air exchange rate”

**Higher risk of bioaerosols
transmission
(COVID-19)**

**Bad Indoor
Air Quality**

Sources of CO₂ emission in indoor environments

1 hour bus ride

30 passengers, sensor at 3rd row

Reached maximum values near 2500 ppm

Study room at home

2 hours no ventilation-1 person **Linearly** increasing CO₂ concentration for 2 hours.

High indoors CO₂ concentration

BAD IAQ & high risk of infection

Ventilation

Case study: “The MICRO-BIO process” transforming indoor air pollutants into valuable compounds

Circular Economy:

Transform an indoor pollutant (**Waste**) into renewable carbon source (**Resource**)

Capture and bioconversion of CO₂ from indoor air: "The MICRO-BIO process"

“The MICRO-BIO process: CO₂ Microconcentrator module”

- **Indoor Air Stream**($\downarrow\downarrow$ CO₂) \approx 800-5000 ppm_v
- **CO₂ concentrated stream** ($\uparrow\uparrow\uparrow$ CO₂) \approx 15 % CO₂ - 90%
- **Treated/clean indoor**/(free of COVID-19) and low CO₂ concentration (\downarrow CO₂) \approx 0-100 ppm_v

Key operational parameters for the CO₂ Microconcentrator module

- **CO₂-MCM:** multiple microchannels covered with an adsorbent material formed by a support material (fumed silica) impregnated with Polyethylenimine (PEI).
- **Alternative support materials:** Fumed and mesoporous silica, mesoporous alumina, clay, ashes from agro-industrial wastes (under evaluation in the lab).
- **PEI-** shows a Good regeneration after multiple adsorption/desorption cycles at low temperature (70-100 °C)
- Heat applied during desorption cycles helps to deactivate viruses such as COVID-19 if:

T > 75 °C, 3 min.

T > 65 °C, 5 min.

T > 60 °C, 60 mins.

Automated CO₂ Microconcentrator prototype roadmap

- 1. Process design: 3D printed CO₂ microconcentrator prototype
- 2. Prototype automation
- 3. Experimentation

CO₂ Microconcentrator module (CO₂-MCM)

3. Experimentation: CO₂-capture lab scale results (iteration 1)

Lab scale CO₂-microconcentrator prototype

- **1:100 scale for an ACH of 4 h⁻¹ (30 m³ room)**
- **200 ml/min Air, 1500 ppm_v CO₂**

Q desorption N2 (ml/min)	C, CO2 max (ppmv)	C, CO2 max (%)
50	75590.20	7.56
20	184472.10	18.45
10	271719.18	27.17
5	262886.73	26.29
2	273324.53	27.33

27 % CO₂, max CO₂ desorbed

Need of better desorption methodology

CO₂ Microconcentrator module (CO₂-MCM)

3. Experimentation: CO₂-capture lab scale results (iteration 2)

Lab scale CO₂-microconcentrator prototype

- **1:10 scale for an ACH of 1 h⁻¹ (30 m³ room)**
- **500 ml/min Air, 5000 ppm_v CO₂**

Tdes (°C)	Cin, CO2 (ppmv)	Q desorption N2 (ml/min)	Cmax, CO2 (%) average	Cmax, CO2 (%) desv est. (%)
80	5000	20	35.28	3.42
		10	40.39	4.84
		5	45.84	4.97

CO₂ Microconcentrator module (CO₂-MCM)

3. Experimentation: CO₂-capture lab scale results (iteration 3)

Side view-

Automated prototype inside a box

Front view-

Automated prototype without the box

II-> III Improve 3D printed box (gas tightness) and prototype casing

CO₂ Microconcentrator module (CO₂-MCM)

3. Experimentation: CO₂-capture lab scale results (iteration 3)

Top view-

Automated prototype inside a box

CO₂ microconcentrator simplified flow diagram

Microbial Electrosynthesis Technology Module

Bioelectrochemical system for CH₄ production (Batch Mode)

Research goal:

- To produce high purity CH₄ stream (90-95 % V/V)

CH₄ (90-95%)

Flat plate BES

Cathode: carbon cloth
Anode: granular graphite

3D printed capillary channels

Internal diameter = 1.1 mm
channel length = 10 cm

Microbial Electrosynthesis Technology Module

Continuous operation electromethanogenic bioelectrochemical system

Lab scale Bioelectrochemical cell operated at 30 °C.

CH₄ max composition 60 %
Goal increase above 90 %

Microbial Electrosynthesis Technology Module

Continuous operation electromethanogenic BES

Assessment of liquid and gas flowrates on the continuous operation

Voltage -0.997 V

Voltage -1.1 V

Work in progress...

Impact of nutrient supply, secondary products removal, pH control through media renovation, CO₂ supply, CO₂ and H₂ availability (gas-liquid mass transfer).

Capillary microbioreactor module

- (A) 3D printed straight capillary column**
- (B) 3D printed curved capillary channel**
- (C) 3D printed curved column top view**
- (D) 3D printed straight column top view**
- (E) 3D printed microbioreactor columns connected in series ensembled**
- (F) 3D printed capillary microbioreactor connected in series test platform.**

Capillary microbio reactor module

Coupling of capillary microbio reactor with bioelectrochemical system

Coupling of capillary microbio reactor in the recycling line to enhance CO_2 G-L mass transfer

Coupling of CO₂-MCM and BES

The carbon needs of the bioelectrochemical system can be supplied by the CO₂-microconcentrator prototype

Microbial Electrosynthesis Technology Module

Coupling of CO₂-MCM and BES

Capture prototype comparison for coupling of CO₂-MCM and BES

Prototype 2 can provide as twice of CO₂ in the same period of time as prototype 1

Next Steps

Automation of BES and coupling with CO₂ microconcentrator

“Portable bioelectrochemical modules for decentralised mitigation of CO₂ emissions using surplus energy (De-Cent)”.

PI: Sebastià Puig. Co-PI: Lluís Bañeras

CO₂ microconcentrator automated prototype

Automated BES module for CH₄ production

- The **capture of CO₂ from indoor environments** stands as an unexplored **source of renewable carbon**, but also as a strategy to improve **indoor air quality**.
- The combination of **indoor CO₂ Direct Air Capture (iCO₂-DAC)** and Microbial Electrosynthesis Technologies stands as an environmentally friendly technological solution to minimize the climate change effects.
- This technology would be suitable to be used in buildings to promote **sustainable design and energy conservation as principles of green buildings design**.

Summary

Do we really can fight climate change through indoor CO₂ capture/conversion?

	School classrooms CO ₂ > 5000 ppm _v
	Office buildings CO ₂ > 1000 ppm _v
	Metro cabin CO ₂ > 3000 ppm _v

1. “Indoor CO₂ is too diluted”
2. “CO₂ is not an indoor pollutant”
3. “We have enough with HVAC systems to remove CO₂”

1. Buildings consume 40% of global energy, 70% in some major cities, and are thus a major contributor to global warming.
2. We spend about 85-90 % of our time indoors. We are indoor species.

What's your indoor age? Mine is 32.4 years.

3. CO₂ capture from indoor environments can help to reduce by 20-40 % in air conditioning requirements.

Indoor CO₂ as renewable carbon source: Coupling indoor CO₂ direct air capture to microbial electrosynthesis technologies

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Terrassa, November 9th, 2023

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101036766

Simulation of virtual use-cases for the research project RESTORE using the web-based process simulation platform IPSE GO

Erhard Perz

NET-Fuels 1st Stakeholders Community Workshop
Leitat, Terrassa Spain, November 9, 2023

RESTORE Project Overview

- **Motivation and Objectives**
- **Restore Concept**
- **Virtual Use – Cases**

Use Case Implementation and the Simulation Platform IPSE GO

- **Requirements**
- **Underlying Basics and Preexisting Work**
- **Capabilities**
- **Current Status and Future Work**

Motivation

- EU Residential sector covers **24.6%** of final energy consumption, corresponding to around **283.9 Mtoe per year**. The largest share is used for space and water heating (**around 80%**). A large fraction is covered by fossil fuels burned in conventional boilers
- District heating (DH) mainly relies on natural gas (**37%**), coal (**25%**) and only renewable energy sources (**22%**) due to their unpredictability and lack of dispatchability on seasonal base
- As result, the space heating sector releases **843 Mton** of CO₂ per year, representing to approximately **26.3%** of the total energy-related CO₂ emissions at European level.

RESTORE Response

RESTORE identified key challenges and gives response to them

Identified Challenges

To develop Energy Storage solutions for daily and seasonal storage

To develop solutions that provides smart, efficient and effective integration of different RES

To develop solutions that can be adapted to the specific conditions of the different geographical regions of EU

RESTORE response

Competitive Thermo-Chemical Storage (TCS)

Flexible Heat Pump and Organic Rankine Cycles (ORC)

Technology which can be adapted to different RES and WHR. To demonstrate replicability (*“virtual use-cases”*)

RESTORE Objectives

RESTORE global objective

to develop a solution

Based on

Combining two
innovative
technologies

TCES
+
ORC/HP

To integrate

wide variety of RES
into
daily and seasonal
energy storage

To allow

DHC networks reach \approx
100% RES in a competitive
and sustainable way

RESTORE Consortium

- **AUSTRIA**
TU Wien, SimTech, Andritz
- **BELGIUM**
Prospex Ins.
- **DENMARK**
Aalborg CSP
- **GERMANY**
STEINBEIS
- **ITALY**
POLIMI, Turboden
- **ROMANIA**
UBB
- **SPAIN**
CENER, Enerbasque

CENER	Coordinator
TU-Wien	TCES experts
Politecnico	Research on HP/ORC
Turboden	Large scale HP/ORC
Enerbasque	Small scale HP/ORC
SimTech	Virtual use-cases & platform
Aalborg CSP	DHC & seasonal storage
Steinbeis	Solites > D&C S2i (LTP) > Exploitation
Andritz	Paper industry expertise
UBB	Life cycle assessment
Prospex Ins.	Social Assessment & Stakeholders engagement

RESTORE Concept

*High temp. RES
(CSP, biogas,...)
High temp. WHR*

RES electricity

*Med. Temp RES
(ST, Geothermal, ...)
Med. temp. WHR*

RESTORE Concept

RESTORE Concept

RESTORE Validation at TRL4

“Virtual use-cases”: virtual implementation of the project’s concept for specific real facilities over Europe, including:

- Concept adaptation to different facilities spread over the EU
- Optimization of the solution (energy efficiency and cost-effectiveness)
- Consideration of the requirements of the final users
- Publicly available in an open web-based simulation platform

RESTORE Use Cases

Six Use Cases considered:

Brønderslev (Denmark)
 Rohrdorf (Germany)
 Mondi (Slovakia)
 Brescia (Italy)
 Holzkirchen (Germany)
 POLIMI (Italy)

Requirements

- Web-based simulation platform
- Allow the virtual implementation of the DHC Use-Cases with real data from the Use-Case providers.
- Make use cases publicly available for interactive simulation by those interested in the technology.
- Stakeholders will be able to create their own testing cases, such that the number of different application examples will grow continuously.
- The platform with the collection of virtual use cases will remain online after the project to stimulate a new technological direction and the emergence of a European innovation ecosystem around the RESTORE paradigm.

Simulation Framework IPSEpro

- Equation oriented process simulation framework
- Defines a generic model structure
- Framework separating domain specific models from the rest of the code. Makes it possible to use the framework for various applications
- Ready-to-use model libraries are available for various applications
- Model Development Kit for implementing new component models
- Separates graphical User Interface from calculation kernel

Serves as configuration tool for the Web Platform

Preexisting Work: MIDES Web Based Platform

- Modeling tool for (project) internal use
- Prototype and proof-of-concept
- Support through Horizon 2020

Simulation Platform IPSE GO

- Generic, re-usable, cloud-native simulation framework
 - Adaptable to different applications through the use of application specific model libraries
 - Allows to integrate in websites (e.g. for dissemination)
 - Support collaboration through project sharing
-
- Full use requires some expertise and is not trivial
 - Important to take into account the needs of different usage levels

Occasional Visitor

- General interest
- Overview, but not interested in technical details
- No (deeper) interaction
- Consumes available information

Basic User

- Basic interest in technical details
- Adjusts some data/numerical values

Expert User

- Detailed interest in the system and its adaptation for specific situations
- Adjusts plant layout

Public Overview Page

Model Library built for the Horizon 2020 RESTORE Project

about.ipsego.app/embed/RESTORE_Lib

Model Library built for the Horizon 2020 RESTORE Project

Overview	37 Available Units	Example Projects
<p>RESTORE – Renewable Energy based seasonal Storage Technology in Order to Raise Economic and environmental sustainability of DHC</p> <p>RESTORE proposes a radically innovative solution for DHC, based on the combination of two key innovative technologies, that allows integrating a wide variety of renewable technologies combined with competitive seasonal storage in DHC networks, allowing them to be 100% renewable to radically improve their environmental sustainability.</p> <p>The first technology the project aims to develop is an innovative thermal energy storage system based on thermochemical reactions, the Thermochemical Energy Storage (TCES), that provides daily and seasonal competitive energy storage due to its high energy density, very low energy losses and its low cost. The system represents a key development due to the fact that it allows harnessing the enormous amount of energy that is normally wasted due to the mismatch between energy demand (loads) and energy generation (related to the availability of renewable resources or waste heat), mainly occurring between seasons. In addition, the project aims to develop a second technology based on Heat Pump (HP) and Organic Rankine Cycle (ORC) combined with the TCES system. This second technology adapts the energy provided by different renewable technologies to feed the storage system, thus a wide variety of renewable technologies and waste heat can be integrated into the whole system to finally supply the energy demand under the specific conditions laid down by each DHC.</p> <p>This radically innovative solution would tackle the main barriers to a wide deployment of renewable energy technologies and waste heat in the existing and future DHC networks. The project considers the experimental validation of the RESTORE concept and also the demonstration of the concept replicability potential, adapting and optimizing the proposed solution to different real sites (different network conditions and local particularities as the available renewable technologies/waste heat) spread over the EU, and quantifying its potential benefits via virtual use-cases.</p> <p>Additional information about the project can be found here: https://www.restore-dhc.eu/</p>		<p>Library Author SimTech GmbH</p> <p>Keywords Thermochemical Energy Storage, TCES, Organic Rankine Cycle, Reversible Organic Rankine Cycle, Heat Pump, District Heating, District Cooling, Horizon 2020</p> <p>Version 0.2.0</p>

Public Library Page

Model Library built for the Horizon 2020 RESTORE Project

about.ipsego.app/embed/RESTORE_Lib

Model Library built for the Horizon 2020 RESTORE Project

Overview	37 Available Units	Example Projects
G_OR_Htex heat exchanger for transfer from gas on hot side to organic fluid on cold side		
mech_loss mechanical loss		
OR_Boiler simple boiler model for ORC fluids		
OR_Condenser_a condenser for ORC fluids, air cooled, dry		
OR_G_Htex heat exchanger for transfer from ORC fluid on hot side to gas on cold side		
OR_Heat_source heat source for usage with OR streams		
OR_Pump pump for ORC fluids		
OR_Sink sink for an ORC stream		
OR_T_Htex heat exchanger for transfer from ORC fluid on hot side to thermofluid on cold side		
OR_Xprescription prescription/calculation of vapor quality of an ORC fluid		

Windows taskbar: 16:24 2023-06-26

Public Examples and Use Cases

Model Library built for the Horizon 2020 RESTORE Project

Overview 55 Available Units Example Projects

Demo_RESTORE_rORC
Demonstration model of the reversible ORC process for charging and discharging interaction with TCES as envisaged within the RESTORE project.

RESTORE rORC HP mode chargi...
Demonstration model of the reversible ORC process for charging and discharging interaction with thermochemical energy storage (TCES). TCES is

RESTORE rORC ORC mode disch...
Demonstration model of the reversible ORC process for charging and discharging interaction with thermochemical energy storage (TCES). TCES is

RESTORE rORC with TCES
Demonstration model of the reversible ORC process for charging and discharging interaction with thermochemical energy storage (TCES). TCES is

TCM_Charging_Step

TCM_Discharging_Step

Use Case I – Brønderslev, Denmark

Use Case II – Gmunden, Austria

14:30 2023-11-08

Public Project Detail View

Model Library built for the Horiz...
 about.ipsego.app/embed/RESTORE_Lib

rORC / ORC and HP Process

ORC and Heat Pump (HP) are sharing the heat exchangers and are using an internal recuperator.

ORC Discharging

Cycle El. Power Output	34642	[kW]
Net El. Power Output	32892	[kW]
Evaporator Heat Transfer	70	[kW]
Condenser Heat Transfer	26.741	[kW]
ORC Cycle Efficiency	11.814	%
Net Cycle Efficiency	10.864	%
Turbine Pressure Ratio	6.62	[-]
Turbine Mass Flow	0.2865	[kg/s]
Turbine Inlet Volumetric Flow	2.8812	[m³/s]
Turbine Outlet Volumetric Flow	10.261	[m³/s]
Evaporator LPA	6.791	[kPa]
Condenser LPA	2.0864	[kPa]
Recuperator LPA	0.7805	[kPa]

HP Charging

Cycle El. Power Input	12.31	[kW]
Condenser Heat to Reactor	30	[kW]
Evaporator Heat Transfer	17.69	[kW]
COP	2.677	[-]
Compressor Pressure Ratio	5.8163	[-]
Compressor Mass Flow	0.6407	[kg/s]
Compressor Inlet Volumetric Flow	26.364	[m³/s]
Compressor Outlet Volumetric Flow	3.0883	[m³/s]
Condenser LPA	6.8371	[kPa]
Evaporator LPA	2.1915	[kPa]
Recuperator LPA	0.7805	[kPa]

Cycle Characteristics

#	p	t	h	x	fluid
[Orb. #]	[bar abs]	[°C]	[kJ/kg]	[-]	
1	14.2	94	382.67	0	NOVEC60
2	14	90.68	338.1	-1.1172	NOVEC60
3	2.32	73.19	338.1	0.8465	NOVEC60
4	2.5	77.907	366.71	1	NOVEC60
5	2.46	124.17	410.18	1.8707	NOVEC60
6	14.26	160.24	429.59	1.2656	NOVEC60
7					NOVEC60
8					
9					
10	2	90	419.17	0	Cooling Water
11					
12	1.9	80	336.06	0	Cooling Water

TCES HP mode - charging

RES + WEH

TCES ORC mode - discharging

DISTRICT HEATING

#	p	t	h	x	fluid
[Orb. #]	[bar abs]	[°C]	[kJ/kg]	[-]	
1	14.2	94	382.67	0	NOVEC60
2	14	90.68	338.1	-1.1172	NOVEC60
3	2.32	73.19	338.1	0.8465	NOVEC60
4	2.5	77.907	366.71	1	NOVEC60
5	2.46	124.17	410.18	1.8707	NOVEC60
6	14.26	160.24	429.59	1.2656	NOVEC60
7					NOVEC60
8					
9					
10	2	90	419.17	0	Cooling Water
11					
12	1.9	80	336.06	0	Cooling Water

#	p	t	h	x	fluid
[Orb. #]	[bar abs]	[°C]	[kJ/kg]	[-]	
1	14.132	94	382.37	0	NOVEC60
2	8.46	89.501	285.08	-1.4224	NOVEC60
3	6.36	83.08	293.66	-0.894	NOVEC60
4					NOVEC60
5					NOVEC60
6	6.28	107.28	403.84	-1	NOVEC60
7	14.725	103.7	391.75	1.4782	NOVEC60
8	14.432	88.501	358.94	1.096	NOVEC60
9					NOVEC60
10	2	38	146.82	0	Cooling Water
11					
12	1.9	88	230.39	0	Cooling Water

Demo RESTORE_rORC
 Demonstration model of the reversible ORC process for charging and discharging interaction with TCES as envisaged within the RESTORE project.

TCM_Charging_Step TCM_Discharging_Step Use Case I – Brønderslev, Denmark Use Case II – Gmunden, Austria

2023-11-09

www.restore-dhc.eu

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Public/Embedded Projects

- Projects can be embedded in any HTML page
 - Not only a picture, actual project editor
- Full access to the project details if enabled. It will also be possible to run calculations.
- Projects with restricted permissions for edition (no change of layout, only predefined values can be modified)
- Data exchange with the surrounding document context.
- “Live Report”

Discover

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed do eiusmod tempor incididunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua.

Discover

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed do eiusmod tempor incididunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua.

Dashboard

Dashboard - IPSE GO x +

ipsego.app

Support About RESTORE User

NAVIGATION

- Dashboard
- Projects
- Groups
- Libraries
- Licenses

SETTINGS

- Profile
- Preferences

My Projects

- New Project
- Import Project
- RESTORE rORC with TCES (Updated 4 hours ago)
- My first ORC process (Updated 4 hours ago)
- RESTORE rORC HP mode ch... (Updated 5 hours ago)
- RESTORE rORC ORC mode d... (Updated 5 hours ago)
- RESTORE rORC with TCES (Updated 5 hours ago)

Guides & Documentation

- Tutorial #1 Simple Stream: Create your first Simple Stream
- Model Library built for the Horizon 2020 RESTORE Project: Library Documentation: RESTORE_Lib

Explore Example Projects

- Demo_RESTORE_rORC
- RESTORE rORC HP mode ch...
- RESTORE rORC ORC mode d...
- RESTORE rORC with TCES
- TCM_Charging_Step
- TCM_Discharging_Step

Windows taskbar: 22:52 2023-10-04

Projects

My Projects - IPSE GO

ipsego.app/projects

Support About RESTORE User

My Projects Example Projects

New Project Import Project

Navigation: Dashboard, Projects, Groups, Libraries, Licenses, Profile, Preferences

Search Projects

Preview	Name	Owner	Library	Changed	Actions
	RESTORE rORC with TCES	RU RESTORE User	RESTORE_Lib	Changed 4 hours ago	⋮
	My first ORC process	RU RESTORE User	RESTORE_Lib	Changed 4 hours ago	⋮
	RESTORE rORC HP mode charging TCES	RU RESTORE User	RESTORE_Lib	Changed 5 hours ago	🔗 📄 🔄 📄 ⋮
	RESTORE rORC ORC mode discharging TCES	RU RESTORE User	RESTORE_Lib	Changed 5 hours ago	⋮
	RESTORE rORC with TCES	RU RESTORE User	RESTORE_Lib	Changed 5 hours ago	⋮
	TCM_Discharging_Step	RU RESTORE User	RESTORE_Lib	Changed 5 hours ago	⋮
	TCM_Charging_Step	RU RESTORE User	RESTORE_Lib	Changed 5 hours ago	⋮
	Demo_RESTORE_rORC	RU RESTORE User	RESTORE_Lib	Changed 5 hours ago	⋮

Items per page: 15 1 - 8 of 8

Project Editor

RESTORE rORC HP mode charging

ipsego.app/project/6921568f-05b2-412d-a27a-9c7e86a57328

Support About RESTORE User

Project View Objects Calculation

Save Download Undo Redo Print Setup Page Measure... Copy Paste Cut Delete Help Feedback Open Doc...

Search Icons...

All

- OR_Sink
- OR_Source
- OR_Connector
- OR_Mixer (3)
- OR_Splitter (3)
- OR_Boiler
- OR_Condenser (2)
- OR_Condense...
- OR_Htex (2)
- OR_G_Htex (2)
- OR_T_Htex (2)
- ORC (OR_) Subsystems
- Gas (G_) Subsystems
- H2O (W_) Subsystems
- Heat Transfer Fluid (T_) S
- Thermochemical Energy
- Machinery
- General

RESTORE rORC HP mode charging TCES

rORC in Heat Pump (HP) Mode Charging the TCES

Heat Pump (HP) used for charging the thermochemical energy storage (TCES).
TCES is preliminary and uses copper sulfate in an oil suspension as working material.

Parameter	Value	Units
Cycle El. Power Input	1.4628	[kW]
Condenser Heat to Reactor	5	[kW]
Evaporator Heat Transfer	3.5375	[kW]
COP	3.4181	[-]
Compressor Pressure Ratio	5.8163	[-]
Compressor Mass Flow	6.791e-2	[kg/s]
Compressor Inlet Volumetric Flow	2.9055	[m³/s]
Compressor Outlet Volumetric Flow	0.4952	[m³/s]
Condenser LFA	0.10711	[m²/K]
Evaporator LFA	0.4932	[m²/K]
Reactor LFA	0.3741	[m²/K]

#	p	T	h	s	Fluid
1	14.2	154	382.27	0	Novec 649
2	14	100.63	313.61	-1.7479	Novec 649
3	2.52	76.19	313.61	0.3343	Novec 649
4	2.5	77.807	365.71	1	Novec 649
5	2.45	149	434.55	1.8505	Novec 649
6	14.25	182.2	456.2	1.9383	Novec 649
7					Novec 649
11	2	100	419.17	0	Cooling Water
12	1.9	80	335.06	0	Cooling Water

Object Manager

Search...

Class	Object
motor	motor002
OR_Compressor	OR_Compressor001
OR_Connector	OR_Connector002
OR_Htex	OR_Htex001_C
OR_Valve	OR_Valve001
OR_Xprescription	OR_Xprescription101
OR_Xprescription	OR_Xprescription102
OR_Xprescription	OR_Xprescription103
OR_Xprescription	OR_Xprescription104
OR_Xprescription	OR_Xprescription105
OR_Xprescription	OR_Xprescription106
TCM_Heat_sink	TCM_Heat_sink001C
TCM_Heat_source	TCM_Heat_source001C
TCM_Mixer	TCM_Mixer001
TCM_Reactor_Charging	TCM_Reactor_Charging001
TCM_Separator	TCM_Separator001
TCM_Sink	TCM_Sink001
TCM_Source	TCM_Source001
W_Heat_sink	W_Heat_sink001C
W_OR_Htex	W_OR_Htex001
W_Sink	W_Sink001a
W_Sink	W_Sink001b
W_Source	W_Source001a
Stream	Stream001
Object Manager	Dataset Manager

100% design (1) Standard

Visual Studio Code

IPSE GO v1.1.14 - RESTORE_LIB

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Use Cases

Example Projects - IPSE GO

ipsego.app/projects/demos?library=RESTORE_Lib

Support About RESTORE User

NAVIGATION

- Dashboard
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- Libraries
- Licenses

SETTINGS

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- Preferences

My Projects Example Projects

New Project Import Project

Search...

Demo_RESTORE_rORC

Demonstration model of the reversible ORC process for charging and discharging interaction with TCES as

RESTORE rORC HP mode ch...

Demonstration model of the reversible ORC process for charging and discharging interaction with

RESTORE rORC ORC mode di...

Demonstration model of the reversible ORC process for charging and discharging interaction with

RESTORE rORC with TCES

Demonstration model of the reversible ORC process for charging and discharging interaction with

TCM_Charging_Step

Preliminary model depicting the charging step of the thermochemical material. Different storage material pairs can be

TCM_Discharging_Step

Preliminary model depicting the discharging step of the thermochemical material. Different storage material pairs

Use Case I - Brønderslev, De...

Use Case I deals with a residential and industrial DH with biomass and solar collectors in Denmark

Use Case II - Gmunden, Aust...

Use Case II deals with the integration of different heat sources into DH of a cement factory in Austria

Use Case III - Ružomberok, S...

Use Case III integrates RESTORE with different heat sources in DH of a paper mill in Slovakia

Use Case IV - BRESCIA, Italy

Use Case IV deals with the integration of different heat sources into DH of a steel industry in Italy

Use Case V - Holzkirchen, G...

Use Case V concerns the district heating with geothermal technology in a plant in Germany

Use Case VI - Milan, Italy

Use Case VI deals with a small-scale DHC network of POLIMI university campus in Italy

< Collapse

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Current Status and Future Work

- Basic Framework is ready to be used
 - Platform is available.
 - Further development is ongoing.
- Work on extended functionality is ongoing
 - Scripting
 - Chart Drawing
 - Time series/dynamic calculations
 - Integration of economic analysis
- Content implementation is work in progress
 - RESTORE model library is being developed
 - Basic components are available
 - Refinements are ongoing

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RESTORE

Renewable Energy based seasonal Storage
Technology in Order to Raise Economic and
environmental sustainability of DHC

Erhard Perz

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101036766

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<https://about.ipsego.app>

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